

Report on design and selection of enzymatic cocktails, optimized protocol and demonstration for the production of sugars from the OFMSW by enzymatic hydrolysis

Deliverable 4.1

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Lead Partner: CENER

Contributor(s): ASA

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The SCALIBUR project aims to demonstrate new valorization routes, such as biobased products, from urban biowaste. Therefore, SCALIBUR enables the formation of a partnership which includes waste management companies, technology developers, researchers and end users; to recover and transform biowaste from three municipalities, Madrid (ES), Albano (IT), and Kozani (EL), into value added products. These new value chains will transform HORECA waste into proteins, lipids and chitin from insect rearing, while the organic fraction of MSW will be hydrolyzed into sugars that will be further converted into biopesticides and bioplastics by fermentation. Moreover, the resulting biogas from MSW and USS (Urban Sewage Sludge) will be upgraded by bioelectrochemical treatment to produce commodity chemicals and bioplastics.

SCALIBUR will create new business models for the resulting circular value chains, applying a sustainable approach to generate new activities and benefits. Therefore, the sustainability of all technological processes must be assessed. This evaluation will include techno-economical, environmental and social levels. Environmental impacts are going to be analyzed through the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) as well as the Social level. The technological developments will be analyzed under an engineering-oriented approach for the techno-economic assessment of the developed processes.

The deliverable 4.1, refers to the definition of the methodologies and performance of the assays in the design of tailor-made enzymatic cocktails and the conversion of the OFMSW into concentrated sugars. This report includes the activities carried out by ASA and CENER within Tasks 4.1 (Production and design of enzyme preparations) and 4.2 (Enzymatic hydrolysis of the OFMSW for the production of sugars). This report is the final version of Deliverable 4.1 (M39) and describes the strategy, the methodology and the results obtained in the design and performance of enzymatic cocktails together with the validation and

upscaling of the enzymatic hydrolysis from pilot to demo scale of the OFMSW supplied by FCC from Las Dehesas plant in Madrid.

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